

Case Study Germany: Irregular Migration and Return

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List of Abbreviations

AVR	Assisted Voluntary Return
AZR	Central Register of Foreigners (Ausländerzentralregister)
BAMF	Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge)
Destatis	Federal Statistical Office of Germany
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
GTAZ	Joint Terrorism and Defense Center (Gemeinsames Terrorismusabwehrzentrum)
REAG/GARP	Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum Seekers in Germany/Government Assisted Repatriation Programme
TCN	Third Country National
ZUR	Joint Return Assistance Center (Zentrum zur Unterstützung der Rückkehr)

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Key Findings of the German Case Study:

- **Federal and decentralised system:** Germany's management of irregular migration and return is split across federal, state (Länder), and local levels, with the BAMF handling asylum decisions centrally while state foreigners' authorities are responsible for enforcing returns. This creates coordination challenges and significant variation in practice across states.
- **Duldung as a significant feature of the German Asylum System:** Germany's tolerated status (Duldung) formally suspends return while leaving the legal obligation to leave in place. With around 220,000 of roughly 250,000 persons obligated to leave holding a tolerated status in 2022, the majority are de facto non-removable.
- **Data quality problems:** The Central Register of Foreigners (AZR) suffers from fragmented legal categories, inconsistent data entry across authorities, outdated records, and systematic under-reporting of departures, which results in an estimated one million entries with invalid or missing information on legal status.
- **Significant divergence between domestic and Eurostat data:** German return figures shared with Eurostat differ substantially from domestic sources. For example, Eurostat recorded around 74,000 returns from Germany in 2016 against roughly 22,000 forced returns in domestic data. The discrepancies stem from definitional mismatches, historicised data overwriting, and likely inclusion of Dublin transfers and assisted voluntary returns in Eurostat figures. Germany's actual return rate has been declining between 2018 and 2022, similar to the EU's return rate. A BAMF study found that two years after receiving an order to leave, the likelihood to receive a residence permit is higher than being returned.
- **Structural reform needs:** We recommend improving AZR interoperability and harmonising data collection across federal states. We also propose creating a statistical "non-returnability" category to separate tolerated persons from the active return caseload, and better aligning German legal categories with Eurostat indicators. These steps would improve both data quality and realistic public expectations about return policy outcomes.

Case Study Germany: Irregular Migration and Return

This case study outlines the case of Germany.¹ It starts by presenting the legal and political context in the field of irregular migration and return. In a next step, it focuses on the core area of inquiry, that is the process of data collection and processing within Germany as well as between Germany and the EU.

1 Legal framework

1.1 Pathways leading to an obligation to leave

In Germany, 'irregularity' can result from **irregular entry, stay, or employment**² (Slootjes et al., 2023). German law enforcement authorities seek to prevent **irregular entry** through two measures – refusal of entry and removal in the proximity of the border following unauthorised entry ('Zurückweisung' and 'Zurückschiebung').³

Regardless of the entry, '**irregular stay**' implies that people are registered by local authorities. Asylum seekers, whose application for international protection was rejected, and individuals, whose legal residence permit has expired, are considered as irregularly staying migrants and are obligated to leave Germany.⁴ People may also stay on the territory irregularly and unregistered following an irregular entry without applying for asylum.

A person's **asylum** procedure in Germany is decided by the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF).⁵ In an asylum context, an obligation to leave can be triggered by three factors.

¹ The authors would like to thank Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, Martina Belmonte, Astrid Nedee and Julia Pingsdorf for their valuable and insightful comments on an earlier draft. We also want to thank Tatjana Baraulina (BAMF) and several of her colleagues for providing background information.

² While an obligation to leave can result from working illegally, this is not the focus of this report. For more information see e.g., Tangermann/Grote, 2017: 48ff.

³ Both processes are to be distinguished from (forced and voluntary) return. Removal following unauthorised entry ('Zurückschiebung') can take place once a person has entered German territory but is still in proximity to the border. The federal police can return an apprehended irregular person to the country through which the person has entered Germany in an expedited manner – as long as the person does not intend to seek asylum. Due to semantic similarity between the terms, and irregularities or errors that may occur during registration, it cannot be ensured that persons who are being subjected to refusal of entry or removal partially show up in other categories of apprehension (cf. Deutscher Bundestag, 2023a: 24). For unaccompanied minors it has to be ensured that they receive appropriate care in the destination country before they are being refused entry or removed (Deutscher Bundestag, 2016).

⁴ The stock of irregular migrants who never registered (i.e. undocumented migrants) in Germany can only be estimated. Based on the Police Crime Statistics, Vogel (2016) estimated between 180.000 and 520.000 undocumented migrants in 2016. Once apprehended, migrants can lodge an asylum application or will be subjected to a return decision.

⁵ A positive decision (in-merit) results in either a recognised refugee status by national law (Basic Law art. 16a) or based on the Geneva Conventions (Asylum Act art. 3(1)). Additionally, there are temporary forms of subsidiary protection (Asylum Act art. 4(1), a form of humanitarian protection) and deportation bans (Residence Act 60(5), based on art. 3 European Convention on Human Rights and less than 10 per cent of the total protection rate). All of these categories combined make up the total 'protection rate', which ranged from 33.2% in 2014 to 57% in 2022 (maximum in 2016 with 62.7%). In contrast, in 2014, 33.4% and in 2022, 21.6% of asylum applications were rejected, while in respectively 35.2% and 22.3% of the cases the BAMF did only take a formal decision (i.e.

- Firstly, a migrant may be ordered to leave if and when an asylum application has been rejected.⁶ For an ‘obviously unfounded’ asylum application, the deadline for leaving Germany is one week. For other ‘simple’ rejections, a person has a 30 days-deadline to leave (Art. 34 and 34a of the Asylum Act).
- Secondly, asylum seekers may also be ordered to leave if the BAMF finds out that another EU member states is responsible for an asylum procedure (according to the Dublin-III-Regulation). The migrant is asked to return to this country inside the EU.⁷
- And thirdly, migrants may have a positive recognition status in another EU member state but have not (yet) the right to move or remain in Germany. They may also be ordered to leave.⁸

Outside the field of asylum, an order to leave can be issued to people who are **overstaying** a residence permit or a visa duration or who lose (visa) rights during a permitted sojourn due to **irregular activities or transgressions** (e.g. a person with a tourist visa starts working). **Other reasons** triggering an order to leave may relate to the withdrawal of legal residence permits due to criminal behaviour (which requires first an expulsion order, articles 53-56a of the Residence Act).

1.2 Consequences of receiving an obligation to leave

Receiving an order to leave has criminal, mobility and financial consequences. In particular,

- A person might face **imprisonment** of up to one year **or a fine** for irregular entry or stay in Germany, which includes overstaying a visa, rendering it a criminal offence (art. 95(1) of the German Residence Act).⁹
- He or she may not move freely within Germany but has to remain in the respective Federal State (art. 61(1) of the German Residence Act). This **territorial constraint** may cease if a foreigner is tolerated for at least three months (the ‘tolerated status’ will be discussed in more detail below).

deciding that Germany was not responsible for the asylum procedure or an asylum application was withdrawn) (BAMF, 2023). The latter triggers an order to leave.

⁶ An order to leave is issued in conjunction with a first instance rejection which can be appealed. The average length of an asylum procedure in Germany was 6.6 months in 2021, with a slight increase to 7.6 months in the first half of 2022 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023b). The time until a decision is reached differs by nationality (see Table 4 in the annex). However, it usually took longer until a judicially non-appealable decision was reached. Judicial appeals have gradually increased the overall length of the procedures from 8.7 months in 2016 to 17.6 months in 2018 to 24 months in 2021. A major reason for the delays is a large number of decisions issued by the BAMF have been “flawed or declared unlawful”. 36 per cent of the original material decisions reviewed by the courts were overturned in 2021 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023b: 1).

⁷ As will be discussed below, the number of return decisions shared by Germany with Eurostat may contain Dublin transfers, even though these are separate categories in Germany and for Eurostat (cf. Eurostat, 2014). We assume that when sharing data with Eurostat, the category ‘persons returned following an order to leave’ contains data from several legal categories, see section 3.

⁸ Administrative courts in several German federal states maintained that beneficiaries of international protection of other member states were in danger of degrading or inhuman behaviour or that reception capacities in other member states were overstretched (e.g. due to the reception of Ukrainian refugees). They thus suspended their removal. In the case of Greece, the processing of second asylum applications was suspended between 2019 and 2022. In 2022, 72 non-Greek nationals were returned to Greece after the German and Greek authorities reached an agreement. In general, the BAMF is not bound by decisions of other member states. A Court of Justice of the EU ruling is pending on the matter (C-753/22) (see also, Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik/Stiller, 2023a).

⁹ Rejected asylum seekers are not fined for staying irregularly in Germany, however, they can be obliged to bear or share the costs of their deportation.

- Foreigners have to **bear the costs** resulting from the enforcement of spatial restrictions, refusal, removal or deportation (art. 66(1) of the Residence Act).

The transposition of the EU's Return Directive led to several changes in the residence laws including a specification of the departure period after an order to leave (between 7 and 30 days), certain safeguard obligations for the repatriation of unaccompanied minors and the introduction of a maximum period of five years for a re-entry ban (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik 2017).

Another possible consequence is detention. An individual who has received an order to leave but is not leaving voluntarily may be placed in **detention** to ensure the return ('Sicherungshaft', art. 62(3) of the German Residence Act). Decisions on detention or alternative measures are decentralised at the federal state level (Länder).¹⁰ Operationally, a detention is usually requested by the foreigners' authority in a Land ('Ausländerbehörde') with the competent district court implying a judge has the final decision-making power (Haberstroh, 2021). Detention is considered an ultima ratio in Germany. Authorities may therefore choose milder forms to monitor affected individuals such as mandatory and frequent reporting requirements, compulsory residence and spatial residence restrictions (Haberstroh, 2021: 4). However, **alternatives to detention** are used rather rarely (see e.g. Ibid: 21). No systematic evaluation of the effectiveness of alternative measures has been conducted – yet, milder means available are often regarded as 'hardly suitable as effective alternatives to detention pending removal' as they might not prevent absconding (Ibid: 38). Court detention orders often do not discuss alternatives to detention thoroughly (Community for all, 2023: 33ff.; Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik/Stiller, 2023b).

Detention has the objective to ensure removal in case there is a risk of absconding. While usually taking shorter, it can be legally ordered for up to six months. If a person is obstructing the removal, the country of origin is not cooperating or in other exceptional cases, detention can be extended for another 12 months. This implies that a maximum duration of 18 months is possible (Haberstroh, 2021: 38). In 2020, there were about 650 places in detention facilities for individuals to be removed (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 33). The number has steadily increased from about 400 in 2017 (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, 2017: 39) to ca. 800 in 2023 and is supposed to increase to about 1000 in the near future.¹¹ About one third of them are located in Bavaria; North-Rhine Westphalia coming second with less than 200 places. A correlation between the number of detention places and an increase of returns has not been found for the case of Germany (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 33). Analyses based on data from the relevant ministries in the federal states show that the number of detentions does not lead to significantly higher returns (Mediendienst Integration, 2023).

In 2017 and 2019, the German government enacted two laws aiming at a 'better enforcement of the obligation to leave the country'. The background was a 2016 terrorist attack on a Christmas market in Berlin killing 12 and injuring 48 people. Prior to the attack, German authorities had failed to deport the man committing this crime (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, 2017: 17). The laws enlarge the possibilities for

¹⁰ For all states there have been 5,475 (in 2012), 4,591 (in 2013), 2,057 (in 2014), 1,327 (in 2015), 2,939 (in 2016), 4,460 (in 2017), 3,848 (in 2018), 4,178 (in 2019), 2,447 (in 2020), and 663 (in 2021) detentions, based on Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, 2017, and own calculations, data from Deutscher Bundestag, 2018 and 2021. Please note that for some states, data can be incomplete, and data can include detention in relation to Dublin transfers and detention pending departure. There can also be over-reporting because some federal states report not only the persons detained in their state but those that have been transferred by other federal states (see also Mediendienst Integration, 2023).

¹¹ Confirmed in an online background conversation by an official from the Bavarian State Office for Asylum and Return, 22.11.2023. Persons waiting to be returned can be transferred over state lines. Other background conversations have been held with officials from BAMF on 10.11.2023 and BMI on 30.10.2023.

state authorities for **'detention pending departure'** ('Ausreisegewahrsam') (notably in case of a perceived security risk of a foreigner). This may be applied in a transit area of an airport or another accommodation and is aimed at enhancing the probability of returning an individual not eligible to enter or stay. Upon court order, 'detention pending departure' can also be enacted even if there is no risk of absconding as it can only last a maximum of ten days in proximity to an airport to ensure return (in that, it differs from detention or 'Sicherungshaft'). There is now also more focus on the level of cooperation of a person in a return procedure (non-departure through no fault of their own). In February 2024, an Act to Improve the Return of Foreigners ('Rückführungsverbesserungsgesetz') has entered into force that extended detention pending departures from 10 to 28 days to avoid absconding; facilitated the issuance of entry bans for persons refused at the border; expanded police search powers when dealing with foreigners; and simplified the return of criminals.

The rejection of an asylum decision, the removal warning and the detention can all be appealed. In case of 'simple rejections' (i.e. if a rejection is not manifestly unfounded, see Fachinger et al. 2024), the appeal of an asylum rejection has a suspensive effect. Between 2013 and 2022, on average two thirds of persons who received a negative asylum decision appealed the decision (ca. 64% in 2022) (BPB, 2024). However, the courts responsible for deciding on asylum and residence (administrative courts) are different from the criminal courts that order prison sentences. Local ordinary courts ('Amtsgerichte') order detention. They are often less familiar with asylum and residence law or the deprivation of liberty cases. This could be one reason why detention orders often turn out unlawful. The different types of jurisdictions between courts have also been 'found to be inconsistent', as this 'contributes to legally unjustified detention rulings' (Mielke et al., 2024: 39 and 44; Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik/Stiller, 2023c).

1.3 Temporary suspension of the return procedure

If a return is not possible for practical or legal reasons and local authorities are aware of it, a toleration status ('Duldung') may come into force, issued by a state's foreigners' authority. Such a status does not equal a residence permit. The enforceable obligation to leave the country ('vollziehbare Ausreisepflicht') remains in place, however, the **return procedure is suspended** temporarily. The duration of the status is set by the foreigners' authority and dependent on the situation of the respective person. It can, in principle, be extended without limits but has to be renewed periodically (usually every three to six months). A person with tolerated status may take up work, generally after an initial period of three months.

In December 2020, around 236,000 persons benefited from a toleration status. Half of them were in Germany for over three years (Haberstroh, et al. 2022). It is important to highlight that the obligation to leave remains in force for people having such a temporary toleration (contrary to the similar system in Austria). Statistically speaking, these people therefore appear like the rest of people having an order to leave even though they are de facto not in a process of leaving or being expelled. There are more than 30 grounds for issuing a tolerated status. The most frequent reasons why people get a tolerated status in Germany are missing travel documents (ca. 25%; June 2023 data), family ties (ca. 10%), an unverified identity (ca. 9%) and reasons upon discretion of the desk officer, which can relate to humanitarian reasons, education, etc. (4.5%). Among other reasons are persons with a subsequent asylum application, deportation bans and health-related reasons, the non-separation of families, unaccompanied minors, and persons in education or work. The biggest category is however 'other reasons' (34%), a category that is used by desk officers for unique or ill-classifiable situations. The large number of people in this category is supposed to be phased out. It has been criticised that there was

no consistent use of this category across states, or sometimes even among foreigners' authorities (cf. Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 15).¹²

Over the last years, **other subsequent forms of tolerated status have been introduced, such as 'Duldung light'¹³ and temporary suspension of deportation for the purpose of training or employment.** For persons with a tolerated status, the temporary forms of suspension of deportation allow a person to stay up to 5 and 2.5 years respectively, and potentially provides pathways to regularisation in case of a successful training ('Ausbildungsduldung', art. 60c) or employment ('Beschäftigungsduldung', 60d of the German Residence Act)¹⁴ (Mediendienst Integration, 2024a). In practice, people with a toleration are not targeted for return procedures.¹⁵

Yet, persons with a tolerated status tend to remain in precarious situations. Their statuses are often prolonged multiple times. Even if they have a toleration for the purpose of training or employment, they are not yet regularised on a predictable timeframe. The length of a toleration differs but tends to be no longer than 6 months per issuance and prolongation. It can be renewed for years – a procedure known as **chain tolerations** ('Kettenduldungen') (Haberstroh et al., 2022). If the reasons for the factual suspension of a return alter (e.g. a clarification of the identity), the procedure may be relaunched by the authorities and a permission regime withdrawn. In principle, **there are three ways out of a toleration status: a forcible or a voluntary return or a more permanent form of a residence permission.** This can include a subsequent application for a protection status (asylum or subsidiary protection), for instance if a crisis situation in the country of origin deteriorates.

In end-December 2022, the German government under Chancellor Scholz provided people with a **toleration status with an additional opportunity to legalise their situation. The law is called 'Opportunity Right of Residence'** ('Chancen-Aufenthaltsrecht'). It pursues the objective of reducing the number of chain tolerations and providing a new pathway to non-criminal irregular persons to acquire permanent residence (Bundesministerium des Inneren und für Heimat, 2022). The conditions for a person are: having been in Germany for at least five years (including time that has been spent with 'Duldung light' status); having always had a toleration status during that time-period; being well-integrated; accepting the liberal constitutional order of Germany; and not providing false information about the own identity and nationality.¹⁶ If all these conditions are met, the migrants may enter an 18-month probation period before becoming eligible for a permanent residence right in Germany. The law concerned ca. 136,000 people who were already 5 years under a toleration regime by the deadline of 31. October 2022 (Bundesregierung 2022). It is yet uncertain if it will be renewed.

In practice, the new law already had a visible impact on the number of tolerated people, who were still considered somehow 'returnable' by the authorities. In Bavaria, for instance, the number of

¹² Cf. Footnote 11. Own calculations based on Deutscher Bundestag, 2023c: 34f.

¹³ Duldung light: Persons without a verified identity who have a tolerated status but do not support the authorities in the identification process can be punished with a work ban, their freedom of movement within Germany can be restricted or their financial support can be cut. Less than 20,000 persons have had this status in August 2023.

¹⁴ These two forms have been respectively introduced in 2016 and 2020 and so far about 15,000 and less than 3,500 persons have benefitted from them. In practice, strict eligibility criteria make it difficult for many people with a tolerated status to receive the status of temporary suspension of deportation for the purpose of training or employment (cf. Pro Asyl 2024).

¹⁵ Cf. Footnote 11.

¹⁶ The law is explained here: <https://www.integrationsbeauftragte.de/ib-de/ich-moechte-mehr-wissen-ueber/chancen-aufenthalt>. There is no clear definition as to what "well integrated" means, but it seems to refer to persons with verified identity who have a good command of the German language and are able to earn a living, cf. Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2022.

people with an order to leave decreased from around 39,000 to 30,000. By January 2024, in the whole of Germany, about 54,000 persons have been granted the opportunity right of residence and at least 75,000 persons have applied for it (Mediendienst Integration, 2024b). In terms of nationalities, about 19 per cent of applications (11,480 persons) have been lodged from persons from Iraq, about nine per cent from persons from Russia (5,460 persons), and about seven per cent from persons from Nigeria (4,052 persons) (Mediendienst Integration, 2024a).

1.4 Competent authorities

Regarding **competent authorities**, the German central level and federal states cooperate with regard to voluntary and forcible returns.

At **central level**, another relevant actor is the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF). Headquartered in Nuremberg, BAMF primarily deals with asylum and integration issues, including being responsible for asylum decisions. More specifically, the BAMF centrally decides on the outcome of an asylum procedure, issues orders to leave for rejected asylum seekers¹⁷ and adjudicates on the existence of 'country of origin'-specific obstacles to removal. It maintains a Central Register of Foreigners ('Ausländerzentralregister', AZR), which is a relevant data source for the field of return (see section below). It also advises on voluntary returns and coordinates and finances the federal main AVR programme called REAG/GARP. Additionally, the BAMF cooperates with regional authorities to get laissez-passer documents (it is also an option that the different states or ZUR can themselves try to get these papers from a third countries).

In concrete terms, the BAMF may first inform an asylum seeker about a negative asylum status and the order to leave (or a person receives an order to leave due to other reasons, see above). Up until the time a person has to leave, a person who is ordered to leave has to comply with certain duties to secure the exit, for instance to adhere to geographical restrictions or submit travel documents (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, 2017: 5). Detention can be imposed upon **court order**.

While the federal states ('Länder') have the responsibility for a forcible return, the German federal police ('Bundespolizei') can support them in terms of acquiring laissez-passer documents, taking the lead in the return to certain third countries, or enforcing refusal of entry and removal following unauthorised entry. A particularly close cooperation between federal and central level takes place with regard to convicted criminals and persons considered a security or terrorist risk. Returning them has been defined a priority in the coalition agreement of the government under Olaf Scholz (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2023b). The Joint Terrorism and Defense Center (GTAZ) and **the Joint Return Assistance Center (ZUR)** usually take the lead to cooperate in such cases. The ZUR was created in March 2017 within the structures of the Ministry of Interior to act as a cooperation platform between the central and the federal structures. Besides representatives of the federal police and the BAMF, each federal state dispatches at least one official to this centre. It deals with issues such as voluntary return, laissez-passer documents, operative issues of return (e.g. charter flights) and security (Deutscher Bundestag 2020).

In practical terms, there are differences between the **federal states** ('Länder') in Germany. A few competences are comparable, however, notably the 'Länder' overall responsibility regarding forcible and voluntary returns as well as Dublin transfers. State ministries (of 'Interior', 'Integration', 'Social or

¹⁷ With regard to visa overstayers, orders to leave may be issued by foreigners' authorities.

Societal Issues’, or ‘Justice’) are in charge of detention facilities and the assistance programmes for return.

Central foreigners’ authorities are bundling the tasks of local foreigners’ authorities and conduct the actual returns. In some states, state police authorities are transporting and accompanying persons to airports. Most often, the federal police is in charge (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 12). **On a local level, the foreigners’ authorities** are issuing return orders, file for detention, and assess the individual reasons that may prevent a removal procedure; this pertains however only to personal circumstances and the practical possibility of enforcing the return by organising the removal. They are also responsible for granting the Opportunity Right of Residence and granting other forms of regular stay, they issue a toleration status and collect data for the Central Register of Foreigners (Ibid.).

Bavaria is the state most active in return. The ‘State Office for Asylum and Returns’ was established in August 2018 to bundle efforts regarding voluntary and forcible returns.¹⁸ It cooperates with and coordinates the individual administrative districts across Bavaria, which have a total of 77 local foreigner authorities and 7 central foreigners’ authorities.¹⁹ The State Office is split in three main areas of activities: voluntary returns; the preparation for forcible returns (e.g. laissez-passer documents or plane tickets); and the return of criminal foreigners. In Bavaria, a foreigners’ authority can indicate to the State Office which individual should be removed forcibly if a return does not take place voluntarily. Foreigners’ authorities check if a return violates the principle of non-refoulement or any other right outlined in the European Convention for Human Rights. If a removal is deemed necessary and operationally possible, the State Office, often in conjunction with the German federal police (Bundespolizei), are the main actors. The federal police may set-up an escort and organises a flight (either a charter flight or a seat in a commercial flight). According to a background conversation with an official from the Bavarian State Office for Asylum and Return (see Footnote 9), Frontex, the EU’s border agency, is not often used in Bavaria for organising charter flights. Its most relevant interaction with local authorities concerns the re-financing of flights (the financial support is usually conditioned on cooperating with other member states).

Non-state actors and civil society organisations are mostly involved in **voluntary return**, notably regarding counselling. In Germany, there are about 600 foreign authorities and 1,500 counselling centres of welfare organisations and non-governmental organisations (Grote 2015, 35). They constitute a wide **network or federal, state, local and non-governmental return counselling and assistance**. The biggest federal programme is ‘REAG/GARP’ (REAG is the Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum Seekers in Germany; GARP is the Government Assisted Repatriation Programme) which is organised by the German Ministry of the Interior. The system provides **financing, travel assistance and medical support**. Since 2017, the programme is complemented by ‘**Starthilfe Plus**’, a programme that can assist with finding accommodation in the country the person is returned to. It also provides additional financial support once a person has returned. Alongside the federal ones, a diverse range of regional and local programmes are available for asylum seekers and persons who have no permission to stay in Germany.

For the **counselling**, local foreigners’ authorities are mostly in charge. Relevant examples of non-state actors are the Raphaelswerk (a non-profit organisation commissioned by the German Bishops’

¹⁸ The website is: <https://www.lfar.bayern.de>

¹⁹ Cf. Footnote 11.

Conference), the Caritas, Diakonie and the German Red Cross, all of which have return counselling centres in several German federal states (Grote 2015, 38). There is no general programme overview available for the whole of Germany on all administrative levels.²⁰ This implies also a lack of coordination between return counselling centres and authorities and no clear standards and quality controls for the counselling. Furthermore, there may also be a difference on the substance of counselling. The counselling by government authorities focuses on the return of a person (and can take place even before an asylum application has been positively or negatively decided upon assessed). State authorities have criticised non-governmental actors to often counsel more on how to remain in and not on how to leave Germany (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 21f.). Another challenge relates to unequal opportunities for returnees. Federal states have divergent systems between different providers of counselling (Feneberg 2019).

Civil society organisations may also get involved to facilitate the transposition of Article 8(6) of the EU's Return Directive 2008/115/EC which calls for independent human rights' monitoring on forced returns. According to the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA, 2022), the German forced-monitoring system is still considered to be only partially operational and less developed compared to other member states. Still, a range of NGOs have taken up monitoring tasks, notably Diakonie, Caritas or task-specific ones such as 'Forum Deportation Monitoring Berlin-Brandenburg' ('Forum Abschiebebeobachtung Berlin Brandenburg'). In such cases, human rights' monitors accompany return operations; they can intervene in case of necessity and later write a report about the operation. Their reports are not public and should provide independent (and internal) feedback for law enforcement authorities.²¹

1.5 International cooperation

A cooperation with non-EU countries is deemed necessary to ensure that the country of origin takes back their own nationals. The non-EU country's cooperation should support the return by providing documents, such as laissez-passer travel documents. **Regarding international cooperation, the German government has been constantly advocating for more formal and informal readmission arrangements at EU level.** The agreements can expedite the return process by requesting documents ad hoc. Germany has been an active EU member state in this regard and was, for instance, instrumental in terms of getting the Turkish government agree on the EU-Turkey Statement of March 2016. It aimed at returning all migrants entering irregularly from Turkey to Greece²² (Smeets and Beach, 2019).

Germany relies on the 18 EU formal readmission agreements. It has signed bilateral implementation protocols for 9 of them to facilitate the work of the foreigners' authorities (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2023a). **The German government has also 31 bilateral readmission agreements (with European neighbours and 16 with non-EU countries including Vietnam, South Korea and Morocco).** In February 2023, within the Federal Ministry of the Interior, the post of Federal Government Special Commissioner for Migration Agreements was created with the objective to

²⁰ This information was shared in an online background conversation with representatives from the Research Centre of the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, 10.11.2023. There is however an overview of federal and other programmes that operate nationally, provided by IOM:

<https://www.returningfromgermany.de/en/programmes/>

²¹ Some NGOs highlight some practices, however, in their annual reports. One example here:

<https://www.diakonie-rlw.de/themen/flucht-migration-integration/jahresbericht-abschiebungsbeobachtung-2>

²² EU-Turkey Statement, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/>

conclude practical cooperative agreements with key countries of origin.²³ These agreements generally do not include Third-Country National clauses, which allow also the return of transit migrants. Formal comprehensive migration agreements ('Ganzheitliches Migrationsabkommen') were signed with India in December 2022 and Georgia in December 2023. Comprehensive migration agreements seek to promote the mobility of students, trainees and professionals, as well as to combat irregular migration and cooperate on return (European Migration Network 2023). Germany has also a few other and return-related agreements, for instance transit agreements for forcible and voluntary return operations with neighbouring and Western Balkan states (see Table 1). Bilateral readmission agreements – if respected – facilitate the process of acquiring laissez-passer documents.²⁴ However, according to our background conversations, no systematic assessment of the bilateral readmission agreements or implementing protocols has been done so far.²⁵

²³ For more information see: <https://www.bmi.bund.de/EN/ministry/commissioners/specialcommissioner-migration-agreements/specialcommissioner-migration-agreements-node.html>

²⁴ Cf. Footnote 11.

²⁵ Cf. Footnote 11. A look at available data for the nationalities in question indicates that the bilateral agreements are not fully respected.

DE-Table 1: Bilateral readmission agreements, other agreements and implementing protocols to EU readmission agreements in Germany with non-EU countries and year signed and entered into force (Cassarino, 2022)²⁶

Partner Country	Year signed	Year in force	Type	EURA in place ²⁷
Albania	2002	2003	Bilateral RA (forced return: 2000)	Yes
Algeria	1997	1999/2006	Bilateral RA	
Armenia	2006	2008	Bilateral RA	Yes
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1996	1997	Bilateral RA	Yes
Georgia	2008	2008	Bilateral RA	Yes
Guinea	2018	2019	Bilateral RA	legally non-binding readmission arrangement
Kazakhstan	2009	2016	Bilateral RA	
Kosovo	2010	2010	Bilateral RA	
Morocco	1998	1998	Bilateral RA (forced + voluntary return: 1999)	
North Macedonia	2002	2004	Bilateral RA	Yes
Norway	1955	1955	Bilateral RA	
Switzerland	1993	1994/1996	Bilateral RA	
Serbia	2002	2003	Bilateral RA	Yes
South Korea	2004	2005	Bilateral RA	
Syria	2008	2009	Bilateral RA	
Vietnam	1995	1995	Bilateral RA	
India	2022	2023	Comprehensive migration agreement	
Georgia	2023	2023	Comprehensive migration agreement	
Armenia	2019	2021	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	2014	2014	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Georgia	2016	2016	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Hong Kong	2004	2006	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Moldova	2010	2010	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Montenegro	2012	2013	Implementing Protocol EURA	
North Macedonia	2013	2014	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Russia	2011	2012	Implementing Protocol EURA	
Serbia	2011	2011	Implementing Protocol EURA	

²⁶ Checked against: Interior Ministry, January 2024, Abkommen zur Erleichterung der Rückkehr ausreisepflichtiger Ausländer: <https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/DE/veroeffentlichungen/themen/migration/rueckkehrfluechtlinge.pdf>

²⁷ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/irregular-migration-and-return/humane-and-effective-return-and-readmission-policy_en

2 Statistical description of the context

2.1 Available data sources on irregularly staying migrants

The German return system is federal and decentralised. This is also reflected in the data production and collection. Additionally, data production differs depending on the legal status of a person. While the BAMF decides on a person's asylum application, state authorities are then responsible to return those people that have no authorisation to stay. In the area of (irregular) migration, three main sources provide relevant data: the **Ministry of the Interior, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, and the Federal Criminal Police Office. The data which these institutions collect is not systematically cross-referenced.** Different databases do not systematically communicate with each other (except for crimes committed by foreigners).

The main database is the Central Register of Foreigners (AZR) administered by the BAMF. It is accessed by all relevant bodies on all administrative levels. It includes personal records on all foreigners who have been in Germany for more than 3 months. At present, data on about 26 million individuals is included either by the BAMF or local and central foreigners' authorities. The data is not publicly accessible and concerns the legal status of a person, the arrival, residency status, work permits, age, gender, education and address.²⁸ Regarding the legal status, the AZR shows whether a person is authorised to stay (e.g. with a refugee status), has received a permit or has been ordered to leave (but potentially is not returned due to a toleration status). It is also registered whether a person has left Germany and whether a person has received return assistance (Hammerl/Janik, 2021).

The AZR shows the **legal status of foreigners**, yet the different statuses of persons who have no authorisation to stay are fragmented into almost 200 different statuses based on the existing legal provisions. This makes it more difficult to share and compare this data beyond Germany (notably with Eurostat). German data is stored in a historised manner which further complicates the comparability of German and Eurostat data. This implies that the data stored for a foreigner may change over time if their situation or legal status alters (data is still available to authorities with access to AZR data, but not available to the public). The data that is shared with Eurostat at one moment in time therefore risks getting changed again within Germany.

This is a particular issue for **orders to leave**. The legal obligation to leave can come from different sources and due to different reasons. We can distinguish between problems regarding the quality of the data and the lack of harmonisation between federal states (and also within federal states). The data can be outdated, overwritten, incomplete or faulty due to mistakes that are made when entering, or due to a lack of updating. This is a pertinent issue for the AZR (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 13). Another major data issue concerns the departure of persons. Even though foreigners are expected to register their departure, people rarely do so. There are only few incentives for individuals supposed to leave for doing so. Persons with a pending asylum procedure, an invalid visa or an order to leave might end their sojourn without informing the relevant authorities. Checks by authorities to see whether a person leaves are not conducted in a systematic manner. Also, persons leaving the country are not systematically registered in the AZR in case authorities are not notified. This can result in an over-reporting of people with an order to leave and an under-reporting of people who actually left, resulting in a flawed overview of the amount of people to be returned. This situation makes it difficult for practitioners to understand, and even estimate, the actual number of people who have to return

²⁸ That said, research institutions can request access to an anonymised sample of the data via the BAMF-Research Data Centre (<https://www.bamf.de/EN/Themen/Forschung/Forschungsdatenzentrum/forschungsdatenzentrum-node.html>) and general overview figures are accessible via GENESIS-Online, a database of the German Federal Statistical Office: <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online>.

or be returned at a given moment in time (Destatis, 2023: 8). Within the AZR, there is the option to register that a person moved to an unknown location ('Fortzug nach Unbekannt') if a person cannot be traced. This can be due to a spontaneous or voluntary return, but also because a person absconded. If a person can be traced again after some time, this will again be registered within the AZR (cf. Peitz, 2013: 7).²⁹

Moreover, the German statistical office (Destatis) has assessed the AZR and concluded that there are about one million AZR entries on foreigners with invalid or no data on their legal authorisation to stay in Germany. This is partially due to a high number of incoming migrants, especially asylum seekers, in 2015 and 2016. Persons fleeing the war in Ukraine as of February 2022, who benefit from a temporary protection are registered as such. The resulting increase of migrants in Germany led to additional administrative bottlenecks that likely affected the overall data quality (Ibid.). Other data challenges arise in relation to the Covid-19 pandemic and Brexit resulting in flawed or missing information on foreigners who entered in a short period of time in Germany (Ibid.: 7f.). Additionally, data on assistance provided to returnees primarily covers the federal assistance but does not automatically show other types of assistance (see above). These quality issues have already been publicly criticised (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 13). Civil society actors are also concerned about the increased interest of data collection about asylum seekers. In view of the flaws mentioned above, they suggest to first fix the data collection and data protection issues before further data is collected (Pro Asyl, 2021).

2.2 Data

Regarding available data, a reliable source is the migration report which the government releases annually.³⁰ It presents data on all aspects of migration, including irregular migration. In terms of incoming migrants, Germany has consistently received the highest number of **asylum applications** in the EU (Figure 1). In 2022, this was a total of 243,835. Asylum applications per 1000 inhabitants have been higher than the EU27 average; in 2016 Germany had the highest number of asylum seekers per 1000 inhabitants within the EU.

²⁹ The authors were unable to verify if or how this change is shared with Eurostat.

³⁰ Migrationsbericht der Bundesregierung, online (12.09.2023):

<https://www.bamf.de/DE/Themen/Forschung/Veroeffentlichungen/Migrationsbericht2021/migrationsbericht-2021-node.html>

DE-Figure 1: Asylum Seekers per 1000 population, 2013-2022 (Eurostat, [migr_asyappctza](#) and own calculations)

In Germany, there are different forms of notification regarding a migrant’s obligation to leave the country, e.g. in the form of a **rejected asylum application** or a removal warning. In terms of ‘orders to leave’, there is no complete or centralised overview of the issuance and use of these instruments. The number of people having to leave is derived from their legal status. If they lose the authorisation to stay due to one of the reasons mentioned in section 1, they are obligated to leave Germany. Figure 2 shows the number of first instance asylum applications in Germany, the number of negative decisions taken each year and the share of negative decisions (BPB, 2024 and BAMF, 2018). It should be noted that the number of decisions does not correspond to the number asylum applications each year. There is a significant backlog, especially post-2015. While the number of officially registered first-instance applications was more than 400,000 in 2015 and more than 700,000 in 2016, the number of migrants arriving in Germany without documents in 2015 alone was about 1 million (BPB, 2024). After a significant drop of asylum applications in 2017, further decreasing until 2020, Germany registered about 217,000 asylum applications in 2022. The share of negative decisions of total decisions on asylum applications reached its peak of about 39 per cent in 2017 and dropped to about 22 per cent in 2022. Another 22 per cent were formal decisions (for instance, a procedure was discontinued, an application was withdrawn, or a Dublin procedure was initiated). This results in a total protection rate of about 56 per cent.

DE-Figure 2: First instance asylum applications, negative decisions and share of negative decisions in Germany, 2013-2022 (BPB, 2024)

Eurostat data, e.g. on asylum applications and orders to leave, differs from domestic data sources (for more on this, see section 3 below). In terms of **total decisions on asylum applications**, the number of first instance decisions on asylum applications was exceeding or on par with the number of illegally found present persons. The number of first instance and final decisions was close to 275,000 decisions in 2022, similar to the level of 2019 with ca. 285,000 decisions. While not all persons who are were ‘illegally found present’ in Germany will apply for asylum in Germany and not all asylum decisions are referring to persons who were previously in the category of ‘illegally found present persons’, this shows that Germany has a continuously high level of decisions being take on asylum procedures in relation to apprehended persons.

Figure 3 contains the number of persons ‘illegally found present’, the number of first instance and final asylum rejections and orders to leave, based on Eurostat figures. It shows an overall high numbers of persons were ‘**illegally found present**’ Germany in 2015 and 2016, and then again with about 200,000 persons in 2022. The aforementioned backlog was due to delayed registrations of incoming persons in 2015/2016 when more than one million migrants arrived in Germany, a number which vastly exceeded the number of persons that were found to be irregular in Germany in that period. The **first instance and final asylum application rejections** were highest in 2017 with more than 350,000 combined rejections. Since then, first instance rejections dropped below 100,000 and were at about 70,000 in 2022.

The **order to leave** is usually issued together with the negative asylum decision, after first instance rejections. Persons that might subsequently receive a tolerated status are included in these figures. The numbers presented here show that orders to leave are, however, approximating the number of

final instance decisions (which are generally much lower than first instance rejections). In 2022, the number of orders to leave was 43,550 and on par with final instance decisions. The comparatively high numbers of orders to leave in 2016 and 2017 can be attributed to the backlog.

DE-Figure 3: Number of persons illegally found present, first instance and final asylum application rejections and orders to leave, 2013-2022 (Eurostat, [migr_asydcfsta](#), [migr_asydcfina](#), [migr_eipre](#), [migr_eiord](#))

There is no comprehensive overview of visa overstayers in Germany. The numbers can only be estimated. Most persons, however, have applied for asylum in Germany and only a small number of persons is obligated to leave due to other reasons (Peitz, 2023: 2; cf. Deutscher Bundestag, 2023b: 68). The available data does not discern on whether individuals with an obligation to leave have to do so because they are overstaying a visa sojourn, lost their residency rights or their asylum application has been rejected. As we can see from Eurostat data in figure 3, we can primarily discern the number of people that are in Germany irregularly by ‘persons illegally found present’ (200,000 for 2022). This can be compared with the rejected asylum seekers (figure 2), where 50,000 persons in 2022 received a negative decision for their asylum application.

In the AZR, there is also an aggregated statistical category of ‘persons without authorisation to stay, tolerated status or permit’. It includes about 350,000 persons present in Germany in 2019 (latest figures, see Figure 4; BPB, 2022 based on GENESIS data, [12531-0007](#)). This category includes persons obligated to leave, visa overstayers, persons who left the country without notifying the authorities. It also contains AZR-entries that cannot be verified or included in other categories (i.e., the number might be inflated due to data errors). We can, however, not infer directly from these figures who has to leave the country because of data inconsistencies. The category obligated to leave is more specific in that regard.

DE-Figure 4: Persons without authorisation to stay, tolerated status or permit, 2013-2019 (BPB, 2022)

German data sources specify the people legally obligated to leave (GENESIS data, [12521-0007](#)). The numbers here have increased substantially since 2013, especially for people with a tolerated status ('Duldungen', art. 60a residence law). In theory, these people have to leave the country (the numbers differ however from 'orders to leave', see below). In practice, individuals who have a tolerated status are not returned. Their stay is tolerated for a specific period of time. The nationalities of persons who have received most tolerated statuses in June 2023 are Iraq (27,954), Afghanistan (16,067), Nigeria (14,110), Russia (13,432), Turkey (10,130), Iran (9839), Serbia (8456), Syria (8329), Pakistan (5962), North Macedonia (5586), Lebanon (5302), Georgia (5123), the Gambia (4939) and unverified identities (6625) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023c).

DE-Figure 5: Persons obligated to leave in Germany, 2013-2022 (GENESIS data, [12521-0007](#))

The numbers in Figure 5 show **the stock of people with an obligation to leave**. It shows persons with a tolerated status (in blue) and others who can be removed (in orange; 50(1) art. and 58(2) German residence law). From the way the AZR is set up and the historicisation of data points, it is not straightforward to infer a flow of persons with an obligation to leave. However, a recent study analysed the cases of people that are obligated to leave after having received a negative decision of their asylum application since 2013. While in 2015 about 83 per cent of the cases relating to obligations to leave had been resolved within 12 months (by return or residence permit or in another way), this was only true for about 26 percent in 2021. This can be attributed to a change in nationalities, and in particular a larger number of people from the Western Balkans with an order to leave in 2015. In addition, it can be partially attributed to travel restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic that were still in place in 2020 and 2021 (Peitz, 2023: 6; 8f.)

When it comes to the **actual effectuated returns**, we see vast differences between the numbers that are shared with Eurostat and the returned persons based on domestic data (Figure 6). In 2016, Eurostat data show that ca. 74,000 persons returned from Germany. By contrast, domestic sources show only a third of that, ca. 25,000 persons. Statistical mismatches in the other direction also occur. In 2022, German sources indicate to have returned about 13,000 persons, while Eurostat shows less than 8,000. It needs to be mentioned that assisted returns may be included in the Eurostat number of returns for Germany. They are not mutually exclusive, yet they also do not make a composite of the Eurostat figures.³¹

³¹ On the 'voluntariness' of voluntary return, see e.g. Webber 2011.

DE-Figure 6: Returns ('Abschiebungen') and return assistance (Mediendienst Integration, 2024c) and persons returned following an order to leave (Eurostat, [migr_eirtn](#)), 2013-2022

Given the abovementioned complications regarding orders to leave, a sensible return rate cannot be calculated based on available German data sources (see more on that below). A return rate can be calculated based on Eurostat data (Figure 7). Here too, however, the reliability of this rate can be questioned.³²

³² Explicitly confirmed by background conversation, cf. Footnote 11.

DE-Figure 7: Return Rate in Germany and total EU-27, 2013-2022 (own calculations based on Eurostat, [migr_eiord](#) and [migr_eirtn](#))

Germany's return rate based on Eurostat data has consistently been higher than the EU's average. In 2016, Germany even reached a level of more than 100% (which is likely due to backlog). These figures can, however, not be replicated based on domestic data, as mentioned.

Regarding **nationalities of persons receiving orders** to leave and actually being returned, we can see a stability within the top 20 nationalities (Table 2).

DE-Table 2: Comparison top 20 nationalities orders to leave and returned persons, 2013 and 2021 (Eurostat, [migr_eiord](#) and [migr_eirtn](#))

Orders to Leave 2013			Orders to Leave 2021		Returned persons 2013			Returned persons 2021	
Serbia	4400	#1	Albania	2515	Serbia	5085	#1	Georgia	1110
Russia	4205	#2	Afghanistan	2415	N. Macedonia	2860	#2	Albania	900
N. Macedonia	1690	#3	Georgia	1785	Russia	1670	#3	Serbia	600
Kosovo	1275	#4	Moldova	1770	Bosnia and Herzegovina	920	#4	Pakistan	515
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1270	#5	Ukraine	1740	Kosovo	790	#5	Moldova	505
Turkey	980	#6	Iraq	1550	Iraq	425	#6	Kosovo	380
Iraq	665	#7	Syria	1440	Turkey	405	#7	Turkey	380
India	650	#8	Serbia	1435	Georgia	380	#8	N. Macedonia	360
Georgia	600	#9	Algeria	1335	Albania	340	#9	Armenia	360
Vietnam	600	#10	Turkey	1145	Iran	255	#10	Russia	325
Morocco	580	#11	Nigeria	1035	Vietnam	250	#11	Ukraine	265
Afghanistan	570	#12	N. Macedonia	1020	China	240	#12	Tunisia	250
Pakistan	545	#13	Morocco	935	India	160	#13	Nigeria	235
Algeria	430	#14	Vietnam	780	Algeria	125	#14	Azerbaijan	215
Ghana	415	#15	Russia	765	Azerbaijan	120	#15	Afghanistan	210
Albania	400	#16	Pakistan	675	Pakistan	115	#16	Ghana	170
Nigeria	360	#17	Bosnia and Herzegovina	640	Armenia	115	#17	Bosnia and Herzegovina	160
Lebanon	320	#18	Iran	605	Morocco	110	#18	Algeria	115
Iran	295	#19	Tunisia	520	Ukraine	105	#19	Iraq	100
Tunisia	275	#20	Kosovo	510	Afghanistan	100	#20	Bangladesh	95

Note: Countries in green have gone up within in the ranking between 2013 and 2022; countries in red have gone down within the ranking.

Third country nationals are predominantly returned to countries in the Western Balkans and Eastern Europe. In recent years, Pakistan, Afghanistan, countries in Central Asia, Northern Africa and Nigeria and Iran have seen high numbers of returns. The absolute numbers of orders to leave and returns has gone down for the top 20 nationalities. This implies that less people are returned and the composition of returnees' nationalities has diversified.

There are different **reasons why removals do not take place**. In 2019, out of about 55,000 planned operations, 57 per cent of return operations have been cancelled. In 36 per cent of cases, the person absconded or could not be apprehended. About 6 per cent of removals are interrupted due to the resistance of the returnee; in less than 8 per cent of the cases, the removal procedure stopped because of the resistance of the individual concerned or the pilot/airline refused the transport. The resistance of an individual may only prevent a removal on a commercial flight but not on a charter flight. Statistically speaking, it is impossible to say whether a single person is resisting, say, five attempts of being removed or if five people have tried each one time. Other reasons include a refusal of the transportation by pilots (1.9 per cent) or the federal policy (1.4 per cent) and legal appeals and health reasons (each less than 1 per cent) (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 25). The information on return flights may get leaked by pro-migrant groups and circulates on the internet weeks before the actual date. As a matter of fact, migrants often hide during that period.

A recent BAMF study analysed the **likelihood of how rejected asylum seekers end their irregularity** or obligation to leave from 2013 to 2022 (Peitz, 2023). Two years after having received an order to leave, the likelihood to receive a residence permit is higher than being returned. On average, after ten years of having an order to leave the country, the likelihood that a rejected asylum seeker ends their obligation to leave by being deported is about 10 per cent. The likelihood of a rejected asylum seeker ending their obligation to leave the country voluntarily or spontaneously (i.e., also without assistance) is about one third. This is more or less the same likelihood for receiving a residence permit and staying in the country. The cumulative likelihood of these possibilities to end an obligation to leave amounts to about 80 per cent after ten years. This implies that for many the obligation to leave is still in place after 10 years (Ibid: 7). This is in line with other research on the 'deportation gap' (Rosenberger/Küffner, 2016). In short, voluntarily leaving a country after having received an order to leave is most likely in the first year. It becomes less likely over time (albeit there are differences depending on nationality).³³ This data indicates that a toleration status may lead to a clearer path to regularity (see below). This is also reiterated by the fact that persons with a toleration status due to education or employment (art. 60 (c) and (d) of residence law) are more likely to be granted a residence permit over time (Ibid: 12).

3 Identified data shortcomings

We will focus on three identified shortcomings (cf. Santamaria/Vespe, 2018; cf. Siruno/Leerkes, 2024). The first concerns the quality of the main register for foreigners in Germany. Second, the tolerated status in Germany makes it difficult to assess how many persons cannot be removed and who legally have an authorisation to stay. Third, data is not fully collected and/or shared with Eurostat in line with the 'Enforcement of Immigration Legislation Statistics' (see Table 3 below). Additionally, there is a difference between the data shared with Eurostat and presented in domestic German sources.

3.1 Improving the Central Foreigners Register, other German databases and data sharing

The data challenges of the AZR have been discussed in different sections of this chapter. They are not new to German authorities, which have already been working to improve the quality of the data of the AZR, e.g. by controlling the comparability of the data available in the AZR and data that is first generated or collected by local foreigners' authorities such as lists of returnees (cf. Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 13f.; cf. Mielke et al., 2024; Destatis, 2022). The AZR does not provide search functions on whether a person is a criminal or a terrorist suspect as it is not connected to the Schengen Information System (which is administered in Germany by the Federal Criminal Police Office). This makes it more difficult for authorities to implement the priority of the German government to concentrate on the return of criminals and criminal suspects.

The local foreigners' authority is in need of the most comprehensive overview of the data landscape. This implies that individual desk officers need to fill different databases, based on the legal and residence situation of a specific foreigner. Also, within some states, there are different databases. In

³³ For instance: overall, rejected asylum seekers from Afghanistan have consistently a higher likelihood to end their obligation to leave by receiving a residence permit than people from Pakistan, even though both nationalities have a high likelihood to end their obligation to leave after ten years. For Nigerian nationals only after five years the likelihood to end the obligation to leave by receiving a residence permit overtakes the likelihood of leaving voluntarily (Peitz, 2023: 11).

practice desk officers may favour one database and neglecting others, thereby not using or sharing relevant information.

At regional level, some state authorities have sought to deal with data challenges on their own. For instance, Bavaria introduced a shared software for its seven central authorities in Munich and the local foreigners' authorities.³⁴ A challenge, however, is that the other 93 foreigners' authorities in different municipalities do not have a uniform or harmonised software for data collection and sharing. The AZR can deliver data on asylum cases and the central authorities can initiate a return procedure on the basis of this information. Local authorities still often use a 'technical pdf' (filling in a document which can be read and used by other authorities), mostly shared via email. There is not yet a software using an interface option for all authorities. The more authorities go up, the more selective the information becomes. A related and significant issue, already mentioned above, is that **persons who have left Germany (without notifying authorities) may still be included in the AZR with an obligation to leave.**

Another obstacle is that relevant data is only selectively published in a readily available, accessible and transparent way and in a form that can be analysed with software (for an exception see BPB, 2024). Data is published annually in responses to parliamentary questions by the government in PDFs and structured as replies to parliamentary questions.³⁵

This all suggests that further reforms of the AZR, notably interoperability of databases and a harmonisation of entering data in the AZR between federal states in Germany, are highly recommended (for more detail see also, Grote, 2021: 68-71; Mielke et al., 2024). Some reforms are already underway. Yet, when it comes to return, the data aggregation can still be improved and harmonised across local levels (within and between federal states). Only once local data aggregation achieves higher levels of comparability and reliability, the focus may shift to the federal and European levels (including Eurostat).

3.2 Tolerated status and the return rate

Out of more than 250,000 persons who are obligated to leave (see figure 4), almost 220,000 have a tolerated status. Most of these people will not be returned in the immediate future. The tolerated status implies that people 'are not, cannot and should not be returned'.³⁶ In practice, foreigners' authorities do not focus on them. In the German case, the return rate is therefore misleading as it includes a large portion of people who are de facto not 'returnable'. This is also a challenge for authorities to make sense of the data with which they are dealing.

As a matter of fact, there may be a stronger emphasis on how to properly identify and deal with the people who are tolerated. A clearer distinction of data about people who cannot be returned and those who may still be returned will inform public debates and create more realistic expectations about a German return rate. We are aware that this is politically challenging as data quality and political priorities can collide in this respect. Migration and return data can be and is used for political purposes, e.g. to call for a restrictive migration policy. Removing people from the database even if

³⁴ Cf. Footnote 11.

³⁵ There is also another political issue. The parliamentary questions have mostly been asked by the opposition party Die Linke. It partially disbanded and therefore lost the right to submit parliamentary questions. Acquiring this information publicly is thus dependent on the questions of opposition parties and contingent on their status in the parliament.

³⁶ Cf. Footnote 11.

they are manifestly not returnable may be politically challenging for any government. **Yet, focusing on how to extract people with a tolerated status from the return data (and return field more widely) will improve the data quality.**

Chain tolerations ('Kettenduldungen') are widely practiced in Germany. Almost 30 per cent of all tolerations are longer than four years; almost 10 per cent go up to 10 years (Rietig/Günnewig, 2020: 16). As mentioned, the probability to leave Germany after several years of a toleration status is low (Peitz, 2023). The provision to create a path to regularity through the 'Opportunity Right of Residence' ('Chancen-Aufenthaltsrecht') has reflected this reality (see Section 1) and could therefore be expanded. Migrants may find themselves in a less precarious and stressful situation with a potentially more predictable path to receiving a regularised status. In addition, this might indirectly have a positive effect on data quality. If expanding the Opportunity Right of Residence is too complex for legal, administrative or political reasons, a temporary 'non-returnability' status could be created in the statistics to suspend the obligation to leave and ensure better data comparability. This may concern people that have no right to stay but that cannot or will not be removed (at least temporarily).

3.3 Differences between domestic and Eurostat data

As shown, **there are pronounced differences between data presented by German sources and published by Eurostat** and the way in which Germany shares data with Eurostat. Return data that is shared by Germany with Eurostat possibly includes Dublin transfers to other member states (Eurostat, 2014). Also, Assisted Voluntary Return can be included in the Eurostat returns for Germany. However, the numbers based on domestic sources do not simply add up to the Eurostat figures. In relation to this, figures on 'voluntary returns' should be separated. Analytically, there is a difference between a voluntary return (in the sense of 'free from pressure'), an assisted return and a return after having received an order to leave.

The following overview in Table 3 shows the differences for each Eurostat dataset, the likely sources of which are threefold. *Firstly*, data in the AZR and other databases may be overwritten as it is historicised data (with limited public access at a later stage). This implies that data shared with Eurostat can be valid at a certain moment but may diverge over time. This challenge is exacerbated by the fact that many categories are presented as stock data and there are significant time delays in their publications. A timely and transparent presentation of data can therefore provide a more up-to-date overview.

Secondly, German data indicators do not always correspond to Eurostat indicators. Therefore, one German indicator has to be divided and/or disaggregated into several Eurostat indicators or the other way round (several German indicators are aggregated into Eurostat indicators). This is caused by path dependencies. German legal (not statistical) categories relate to the residence status of a foreigner. The main database, the AZR, is a register of foreigners and not of irregular migrants in Germany. Reforming the database and aligning it more to the Eurostat categories is a difficult and seems to be more a long-term objective, with data challenges at local level currently being prioritised.³⁷ For instance, 'orders to leave' is a statistical category of Eurostat, whereas 'obligation to leave' is a legal category within the German system that can be counted in different ways. The number of obligations to leave in Germany does not add up to 'orders to leave' in Eurostat (disregarding that the number of obligations to leave cannot easily be counted).

³⁷ As highlighted in a background conversation, cf. Footnote 11.

Thirdly, the different legal categories can also be analysed in multiple ways. Given that the German federal system is complex, an equivalent to a (Eurostat) statistical category does not always exist. A comparison is therefore difficult. For instance, when it comes to calculating a return rate, both a value for orders to leave and for persons being returned needs to be present (cf. Belmonte et al., 2021). Based on data provided by domestic sources, it can be difficult to assess the number of persons who have received an order to leave (as discussed, there is not clear picture of who has to leave and who can be returned). It can be difficult to assess who actually left (given that voluntary return might be included and spontaneous returns are not systematically registered). Similar issues arise for other statistical categories. This complicates the comparison of the German data and Eurostat (and a comparison of German data with most other member states).

DE-Table 3: Indicators and data categories relating to irregular migration in Germany and availability of German data to Eurostat datasets³⁸

Indicator	Data provider	Definition	How data is collected	Corresponding Eurostat indicator (if any)	Comparability with Eurostat
Irregular entry					
Refusal of entry ('Zurückweisung')	Federal police and State authorities	refusal of entry at the border	Federal and state police, shared with State authorities	Partially, 'illegally found person'	
Removal following unauthorised entry ('Zurückschiebung')	Federal police and State authorities	return to country from which the person has entered, in proximity to the border (if no asylum application filed)	Federal and state police, shared with State authorities	Partially, 'illegally found person'	
Irregularly staying TCN					
Persons found to be illegally present	Federal and State police (Police Crime Statistics and until 2017 also EASY-system, so related to asylum applications)	Police Crime Statistics: "illegal entry"; but unclear whether they are taken out after they apply for asylum	Federal and state police, shared with State authorities	Yes, regarding illegal entry and apprehended for "Persons found illegally present"	Eurostat indicator
Rejected asylum seekers (first instance)	BAMF	Asylum application rejected	Administrative data registered as outcomes of the asylum procedure but can be differentiated if a person received a residence status at a later stage (e.g. regularisation following a tolerated status)	Yes	Eurostat indicator
Rejected asylum seekers (final instance)	BAMF	Asylum application rejected after legal appeal	Administrative data based on court decision	Yes	Eurostat indicator

³⁸ While there are pronounced differences between domestic data sources and data presented by Eurostat, it is often unclear how they occur (for more on this see section 3). The authors' contact requests for further information on this have not been responded positively by the responsible units within the German Ministry of the Interior. We therefore cannot verify for several categories whether the information that was provided in background conversations and that we collected in Table 3 is correct. All mistakes are our own.

'Ausreisepflicht'	legal category that results from Ausreiseanweisung	Legal category of person with obligation to leave	Contains all people that have an obligation to leave/no legal reason to stay within Germany. This can result from a rejected asylum application, but also includes overstayers, etc.	Partially, 'Third country nationals ordered to leave'	
'Ausweisungsverfügung'	BAMF, Central Foreigner's Registry (AZR), data entered by state authorities	Order to leave the country after not obligation to leave has been determined	Decided by BAMF and resulting from rejected asylum application	Partially, 'Third country nationals ordered to leave'	
'Abschiebungsandrohung'	Decision by state authorities based on BAMF rejected asylum seeker	Deportation order	Decided by BAMF and enforced by state authorities	Partially, 'Third country nationals ordered to leave'	
Irregular staying TCN who received OTL					
Migrants in detention centres (Sicherungshaft, Abschiebehaft, Ausreisegewahrsam)	State authorities	persons with obligation to leave within the time limit before they have to leave	state authorities on the basis of police authorities apprehended the respective persons	No	
Migrants subject to alternatives to detention	State authorities	depending on the measures this might be included in AZR but no uniform handling of data here		No	
Exit from the irregularly staying					
Persons returned	State authorities and Federal Police	no uniform definition, defined by how person is being returned, if person leaves voluntarily, obligation to inform authorities	see definition, generally included in AZR	Persons returned	Discrepancies in the data
Forced returns	not easily distinguishable, see above				
Voluntary returns	not easily distinguishable, see above				
Returns occurring under a bilateral agreement	not available				
Laissez-passer requested and obtained (and whether bilateral agreement present)	not available				
Duldung	State authorities	Person obligated to leave, but due to different reasons (temporarily) cannot be returned	State authorities in AZR	Unique to Germany	Unique to Germany
Eurostat Datasets and availability					
Third-country nationals refused at border				available	
Third-country nationals found to be illegally present				available	
Third-country nationals who are subject to an obligation to leave				available	
Third-country nationals effectively returned by type of return and citizenship				not available	
Third-country nationals effectively returned to a third country by type of return and citizenship				only available for 2018	
Third-country nationals effectively returned by type of assistance received and citizenship				not available	

Third-country nationals returned to a third-country by type of agreement procedure and citizenship	not available
Third-country nationals returned to a third-country by destination country and citizenship	not available

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Annex

DE-Table A1: Average time in months until decision in asylum procedure is reached by nationality in 2021 (Bundestag, 2022: 11)

Nationality	Time until decision in months
Nigeria	14.9
Somalia	14
Russia	12.1
Iran	11.8
Ghana	10.2
Senegal	10.2
Eritrea	8
Iraq	7.6
Turkey	7.2
Pakistan	6.8
Unidentified	6.7
Afghanistan	6.4
Kosovo	5.9
Tunisia	5.5
Syria	4.8
Morocco	4.7
Algeria	4.5
Serbia	3.2
Georgia	2.8
Albania	2.7
North Macedonia	2
Montenegro	1.9
Bosnia Herzegovina	1.6
Moldova	1.3